

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 -2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4808 (Print)

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<http://www.arseam.com>

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DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES AND EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF TRIBES IN ODISHA

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Abstract

Objective of the paper is to analyse the broad features and educational status of tribes in Odisha. Odisha has the largest percentage of tribals which accounts 22.8 percent of the total population of the state. More than one third of the area of the state is declared as "Scheduled area" with not less than 50per cent concentration of tribes. These areas include the entire district of Koraput, Mayurbhanj, Sundargarh and parts of Ganjam and Boudh, Kandhamal. Thus the tribal population in the state is spread over more than 44per cent of its geographical area. Only 52.24 percent of tribals are literate against the state percentage of 72.9. Education is the key to tribal development.

Key Words- Demography, Education, Population, Poverty, Tribe

Introduction

Odisha is one of the most thickly tribal populated states of India. Baring the state of Nagaland where all Naga groups are declared as the Scheduled tribes, Odisha has the largest percentage of tribals which accounts 22.8 percent of the total population of the state. It is one of the most ethnographic states of India. It has been the home of as many as 62 different tribal communities The tribes are heavily concentrated in Dhenkanal, Gnjam, Kandhamal, Keonjhar, Koraput, Malkangiri, Mayurbhanj, Nawarangpur, Rayagada, Sambalpur and Sundargarh districts. Tribals of Odisha follow the traditional method of cultivation besides the primitive practice of hunting, gathering foods and collecting minor forest produce. Out of 62 types of tribes, 12 types are identified as the Primitive Tribal Groups. These primitive tribes are the Bihor, Bondo, Didayl, Dangaria Kandh, Hill Khaira, Juang, Kutia Kandh, Lanjia Saora, Lodha, Mankidia, Pauri Bhuyan, and the Saora which are heavily concentrated in Dhenkanal, Ganjam, Kandhamal, Kalahandi, Keonjhar, Koraput Malkangiri, Mayurbhanj, Sambalpur and Sundargarh districts.

Demographic Features of Tribal Population in Odisha

In Odisha scheduled tribe population as per the census 2011 constituted 22.8 percent of the state's total. According to 2001 census, it was 22.13 percent. On comparison, it is found

that there has been an increase of 0.67 percent. At the same time, the total population of the scheduled tribes in Kandhamal, district was 53.6 percent of the total population.

Table-1 District wise distribution of Scheduled Tribe Population in Odisha in 2001

Sl.No	State/District	Total Population ('000 nos)	ST Population(in nos)			Percentage of ST population
			Total	Male	Female	
	Odisha	36,804	8,145,081	4,066,783	4,078,298	22.1
1	Mayurbhanj	2,223	1,258,459	631,149	627,310	56.6
2	Sundargarh	1831	918,903	458,815	460,088	50.2
3	Keonjhar	1562	695,141	348,666	346,475	44.5
4	Koraput	1181	585,830	290,306	295,524	49.6
5	Nabarangpur	1026	564,480	282,472	282,008	55.0
6	Rayagada	831	463,418	224,908	238,510	55.8
7	Kalahandi	1335	382,573	188,646	193,927	28.6
8	Kandhamal	648	336,809	166,283	170,526	52.0
9	Sambalpur	936	322,770	161,756	161,014	34.5
10	Malkangiri	504	289,538	143,498	146,040	57.4
11	Balangir	1337	275,822	137,442	138,380	20.6
12	Gajapati	519	263,476	128,679	134,797	50.8
13	Bargarh	1346	260,691	131,145	129,546	19.4
14	Balasore	2024	228,454	116,193	112,261	11.3
15	Nuapada	531	184,221	90,901	93,320	34.7
16	Jharsuguda	510	159,757	80,760	78,997	31.3
17	Dhenkanal	1067	136,501	69,356	67,145	12.8
18	Angul	1140	132,994	67,386	65,608	11.7
19	Jajpur	1624	125,989	64,198	61,791	7.8
20	Khurda	1877	97,186	50,431	46,755	5.2
21	Deogarh	274	92,103	45,961	46,142	33.6
22	Ganjam	3161	90,919	45,843	45,076	2.9
23	Cuttack	2341	83,591	42,800	40,791	3.6
24	Sonpur	542	52,978	26,786	26,192	9.8
25	Nayagarh	864	50,836	25,778	25,058	5.9
26	Boudh	373	46,557	23,276	23,281	12.5
27	Bhadrak	1334	25,141	12,839	12,302	1.9
28	Jagatsinghpur	1058	8,640	4,605	4,035	0.8
29	Kendrapara	1302	6,822	3,550	3,272	0.5
30	Puri	1503	4,482	2,355	2,127	0.3

Source: Census of India, 2001

The percentage of scheduled tribe population to the total population of Kandhamal district in 2001 was 51.96 percent indicating a increase of 1.64 percent in 2011. The total population and tribal population of the state of Odisha and the tribal population of districts with percentage from 2001 to 2011 census. Odisha has the second largest tribal population in India in terms of absolute size next to Madhya Pradesh. As per the 2001 census tribal population is 22.13 per cent of the total population in the state. As per Census data from 1981 to 2001 their decadal growth rate declined from 22.43per cent to 22.13per cent. It has also the largest variety of ethnic groups numbering 62 tribal races next only to Assam. More than one third of the area of the state is declared as "Scheduled area" with not less than 50per cent concentration of tribes. These areas include the entire district of Koraput, Mayurbhanj, Sundargarh and parts of Ganjam and Boudh, Kandhamal. Thus the tribal population in the state is spread over more than 44per cent of its geographical area. The details of tribal population in different district of Odisha are given in table -1. As per the 2001 census data, Mayurbhanj has the second largest ST population i.e. 56.6per cent following Malkangiri with 57.4 per cent. Puri has lowest percentage of ST population that is only 0.3per cent.

Sex Ratio

Out of the total scheduled tribe population of the state, the percentage of male and females in 2011 constituted 49.29 and 50.71 respectively. In 2001 the percentage of male and female of scheduled tribe population constitute 49.93 and 50.07 respectively. In the Kandhamal district, the percentage of scheduled tribe male and female in 2011 constituted 48.5 and 50.63 respectively. The number of females per thousand of males (sex ratio) in Kandhamal district in 2011 was 1037 where as in the state it was 979. One of the remarkable facts about the sex ratio is that the number of females is higher in the scheduled tribe population. The sex ratio of scheduled tribe population in the district is found to be 1062 as against 1029 for all Odisha in 2011. The density of population in Odisha was 236 in 2001 census and has been increased to 270 in 2011 census. This is quite low in comparison to the all India figure of 382 in 2011 census. The density of population in the Kandhamal district is 91 persons as against 270 for the state per square kilometer as per 2011 census which is lowest of all thirty districts of the state of odisha.

Rural- Urban Break-up

An analysis of the rural-urban distribution has been expressed in the Table 3.5. The percentage of the rural tribal population in Kandhamal district in 2011 is 96.89 and in 2001 it was 98.14 percent as against the rural general population of 90.10 and 93.20 percent respectively. About 3.11 percent of the scheduled tribes in Kandhamal district in 2011 and 1.86 percent of scheduled tribe in 2001 were living in the urban areas against the urban general population 9.9% and 6.80% respectively. Tribes constituting 6.21% and 5.49% in the state were living in the urban areas in 2011 and 2001 respectively as against the urban general counterpart 16.7 percent and 14.89 percent respectively. Reduction of rural population and increase in the urban population is a symptom of urban bias in development.

Socio-Cultural Base and Language

The scheduled tribes of Odisha have a strong social and cultural base. There was a misconception that the tribal communities of Odisha do not possess languages but dialects. But linguists claim that the tribes do possess languages. Tribal languages contain the same features which other languages possess such as (i) duality in structure (phonemic and morphemic) (ii) productive capacity (creativity and novelty) (iii) arbitrariness (no correlation between linguistic morphs and their meanings) (iv) interchangeability (vocal and auditory functions are simultaneous) (v) specialization (codes and code switching capability) (vi) displacement (abstractness of speech) (vii) preverification (ability to misrepresent reality) and (viii) cultural transmission (learning and inculcation. Besides tribal languages have all four subsystems such as (i) phono-morphemic (ii) syntactic (III) semantic and (iv) symbolic which other languages have. The major difference between the tribal and non-tribal languages is that the former are unwritten ones, and therefore have no literacy traditions, but only oral. Tribes of the Kandhamal district belong to the Dravidian language group. Kandhas are the principal inhabitants in the district. They speak 'Kui' or 'Kuwi' language. This is their mother tongue. But most of the tribes of the district speak Odia. The Kui language has no script of its own. It has some similarity with odia language in vocabulary.

Religion and Marriage

About 97.5 percent of the tribal population in Odisha are Hindus and 2.5 percent are Christians. Christianity has spread in Ganjam, Koraput, Kandhamal and Surndargarh districts and quite a good number of tribal's belonging to to Kandha, Saora, Oraon, Munda, Khaira and Santal tribe have embraced Christianity. However, inspite of the growing impact of Christianity, some tribes like Bathudis, Bhunjias, Bondas, Juangs and Koyas have remained unaffected by its influence. In order to appease the local deities and to ensure safety and security against disease and death the tribals spend a major portion of their income in ritual and sacrifices. Assimilated tribals in plains like Bathudi, Bhuyan etc get

services of Brahmins. But all the tribes have secular heads for their own tribesmen who perform the village rituals on a communal basis. The post of the traditional tribal priest is usually hereditary. The most common form of marriage among the tribals is arranged one. But marriages by capture and service are also prevalent among the tribes. Polygomy is widely prevalent among them. The system has been accepted as a sign of prestige and it enhances social status of those who have accepted polygomy.

Role of Women and other members of the family

The women in the tribal society occupy a distinctive position in their family. The tribal women perform household work, rear children, prepare food, collect fire-wood from the nearby forest. They also get equal prominence in their festivals and ceremonies. Being economic asset of the family, the women are highly respected and honoured. The older people exercise greater influence over the younger ones. Through the socialization process, youngest people acquire their knowledge through training and learning the methods of cultivation, social norms, behaviour and values. Both the boys and girls participate in ceremonial functions and get equal share along with elders. The adolescent and young assist their parents in fields, in climbing hill tops, in fetching water, in tending cattles, in ploughing fields, in skinning animals etc. The girls help their mothers in cooking, taking care of children, preparing beads, necklaces, plastering walls and floors and the like. A major portion of the village habitat is hilly and forested. Tribal villages are generally found in areas away from the alluvial plains close to rivers. Most of the villages are unethnic in composition and smaller in size. The village head is the chief of the village. All the problems of the village are solved by the village committee called by the village head.

Merry making, Rites and Rituals

Dancing and singing are their pastime while smoking and drinking are their personal habits. During ceremonial dances, colored clothes of cotton and silk are tied as turban by men. Women hold peacock – plumes in their head while dancing. The primitive tribes like the Bondo were not dress in cotton or silk rather they were using the natural fibre. In course of development they have been using the cotton and silk dresses and sarees. Tribals perform several religious rites. Most of the rituals are common in nature. During worship various animals like pig, buffalo, fowl etc are sacrificed before deities along with offering liquor. They believe that any negligence or omission in religious practice causes harm to the family. They feel that without blessing of ancestral cults nothing can go rightly in this world. Therefore they appease them with sacrifice for the benefit of the family, community, village and better harvest of the crops.

Economy

Tribal economy is subsistence type as it basically depends on collecting, hunting and fishing or a combination of hunting and collecting with shifting cultivation. There are tribes like Khaira, Mankidia, Birhor, Kuttia Kandha etc who live in the forest of Mayurbhanj, Keonjhar, Sundargarh and Kandhamal districts exclusively depend on forest resources for their livelihood by practicing hunting, gathering and collecting. They live in temporary hut made out of the materials found in the forest. The Koya is the lone pastoral and cattle-breeder tribal community in Odisha which are concentrated in Koraput and Malkangiri district. The Mahali and Kol-Loharas practise crafts like basketry and blacksmithy respectively. The loharas with their traditional skill and primitive tools manufacture iron and wooden tools for other neighboring tribes and thereby take out their existence. The Bhuyan, Bondo, Dharua, Didayi, Kandha, Kuttia Kandha, Koya, Parenga and Saora practise shifting cultivation. The tribes like Bhumij, Gond, Ho, Kandha, Mirdha, Munda, Oraon, Santal, Saora etc are settled agriculturists, though they supplement their economy with hunting gathering and collecting. Some tribes are also engaged in mining and industrial sector for earning a secured living through wage-labour.

Level of Literacy and Education

Tribals in Odisha are backward in terms of literacy and education. Only 52.24 percent of tribals are literate against the state percentage of 72.9. The literacy rate of the Kandhamal district is 64.1 percent. The literacy rate for the rural population is 51.9% against 86.8% for the urban population. The literacy rate for female is as low as 51.9% where it is 69.8% for male. The literacy rate for ST male is 43.93 and ST female is 11.56 percent. The average literacy rate in the blocks under study (Baliguda, Chakapad, Tikabali and Tumadibandha) on the basis of 2001 census was 48.91 percent.

Educational Status Of Tribes In Odisha

Southern Odisha constitutes the highest tribal population in the state with a very low percentage of literate people. The literacy rate for the ST population in Odisha according to 1991 census is 22.31 per cent as against the state literacy rate of 49.09 per cent. The ST female literacy rate of the state is 10.21 per cent which is lower than the ST male literacy rate of 34.44 per cent. The rate of literacy among the STs is 37.37 per cent against the overall literacy rate of 63.08 per cent in the State as per 2001 Census. The Tribal male and female literacy rates are 51.48 per cent and 23.37 per cent respectively. Over the last decade there has been a significant improvement in literacy level among the STs in Odisha, which recorded a jump from 22.31 per cent in 1991 to 37.37 per cent in 2001 Census.

Table-2 Literacy among Scheduled Tribe Population, State/ District: 2001

Sl.No	State/ District	Total literacy	Literacy rate of ST	Difference
	Odisha	63.08	37.37	25.71
1	Baragarh	63.99	50.21	13.78
2	Jharsuguda	70.65	57.23	13.42
3	Sambalpur	67.25	52.67	14.58
4	Debagarh	60.36	45.26	15.1
5	Sundergarh	64.86	52.75	12.11
6	Kendujhar	59.24	40.30	18.94
7	Mayurbhanj	51.91	38.80	13.11
8	Balasore	70.56	31.88	38.68
9	Bhadrak	73.86	27.44	46.42
10	Kendrapora	76.81	40.07	36.74
11	Jagatsinghpur	79.08	48.62	30.46
12	Cuttack	76.66	35.75	40.91
13	Jajpur	71.44	31.41	40.03
14	Dhenkanal	69.42	39.41	30.01
15	Angul	68.79	45.36	23.43
16	Nayagarh	70.52	47.09	23.43
17	Khurda	79.59	49.91	29.68
18	Puri	77.96	58.72	19.24
19	Ganjam	60.77	35.54	25.23
20	Gajapati	41.26	27.77	13.49
21	Kandhamal	52.68	44.47	8.21
22	Boudha	57.73	46.65	11.08
23	Sonepur	62.84	52.16	10.68
24	Bolangir	55.70	43.64	12.06
25	Nuapada	42.00	33.12	8.88
26	Kalahandi	45.94	34.17	11.77
27	Rayagada	36.15	20.23	15.92
28	Nabarangpur	33.93	24.00	9.93
29	Koraput	35.72	18.68	17.04
30	Malkangiri	30.53	14.69	15.84
	<i>Mean</i>	46.03	22.87	
	<i>SD</i>	14.46	8.49	
	<i>C.V.</i>	31.41	37.12	

Source : Census of India,2001

Odisha was a pioneer state in initiating special types of Residential Educational Institutions for Scheduled Castes/Scheduled Tribes students' educational development. There are 163 Residential High Schools for boys and 55 schools for girls. There are 112 ashram schools for boys in the state and 37 for girls. The state has 143 primary schools with residential facilities and 919 Sevashrams schools, which are non-residential. The state has also established 7 Special Scheduled Tribes Hostels. Four model tribal schools have been established using the Nayodaya Vidyalaya Scheme. The number of students in educational institutions, managed by the Department, in the years 1999-2000, was 131,474 for Scheduled Tribe students and 44,874 for Scheduled Caste students (Government of Odisha, 2006). Odisha constitute the 9.7 per cent of the total tribal population. But the literacy rate is considered below the national average at (47.1 per cent) and the state average at (63.08 per cent). Male literacy has increased from 34.4 per cent to 51.5 per cent while the female literacy rate has gone up from 10.2 per cent to 23.4 per cent during 1991-2001. The literacy rate of ST population in the state has 37.4 per cent according to 2001 census. The coefficient of Variation among districts in tribal literacy in Odisha is 37.12. (Table-2) Across districts, as per 2001 census, the overall literacy rate is the highest in Khurda District at 79.59 percent (Non-Scheduled District) and lowest in Malkangiri District at 14.69 percent (Scheduled District). Difference in tribal literacy from overall literacy is highest in Cuttack and Jajpur district.

Growth of Enrolment

In Odisha, the number of students in primary education increased by 19 times between 1947-48 and 2003-04 (Human Development Report, Odisha 2004). Currently (2003-04), there are 4.9 million children enrolled in primary schools. However, when we compare the decade of the 1980s to that of 1990s, there has been a virtual stagnation in the average annual rate of growth of enrollment i.e 2.7 percent and it increased to 2.8 percent during the period 1990-91 to 2003-04. The scheduled tribe enrolment is always lower than the enrolment of other communities. It is found that in the non-scheduled districts the enrolment in primary level among the ST children is 13 percent while in the scheduled districts the enrolment of ST is 49.5 percent which is quite obvious. The enrolment of ST in the state has either remained constant or has declined over the years, which is a matter of concern.

Conclusion

It is a fact that the development of the tribals is taking place in Odisha, but the pace of development has been rather slow. Unless the pace of development of the tribals is speeded up, the all-round development of the tribals cannot be achieved to the desired level within a reasonable time frame. Education is the key to tribal development. It is observed that enrolment of children in school is very low and dropouts in the school among tribal children in Odisha are alarmingly high. The main reason of this is that the school timing and the working hour of the tribals normally clash and since the tribal children help support their parents in earning, they either do not enroll in the school or dropout if enrolled. Hence, one of the first requirements to ensure better rate of enrolment and higher retention of school children among the tribals is to change the school timing looking at the work schedule of the tribals. Tribal children have very low levels of participation and success in school education programmes. The Educational status of Tribes in Odisha can only be increased by establishment of more tribes' schools and fully residential schools with free dress, food, books and utensils. The tribal villages should have a special drive by the Angan wadi workers to bring all the dropout school children to the schools. Since higher education among the tribes is less, special ST scholarships should be provided to the tribal students perusing higher education, particularly in medical, engineering, agriculture and other vocational streams. Thus, education plays a crucial role in increasing the level of awareness among the tribes. The right to education for ST has not been duly guaranteed so far. They are needed to be educated through social mobilisation generated by education. The literacy campaigns in tribal areas have proved enormous impact on the other social sectors,

most notably women's empowerment, health and population stabilization along with environmental awareness.

It may be concluded that Education, Health and Economic development are very closely related specially in tribal area of Odisha. Rapid economic growth of the state is not possible without improving the quality of life of the tribes of the state. Teachers must be sensitized to the cultural and behavioral strengths of tribal children and motivated to do their best for them in schools. Incentives should be initiated to attract effective teachers to work in tribal schools and to retain them there. Only such motivated teachers are likely to generate interest among tribal children towards schools education by attempting to link the contents of the curriculum with the existing realities of tribal communities through the use of innovative technologies.

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